

BioValue

D5.1 Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

WP 5 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

T 5.1 Identification, analysis and Intellectual Property Right assessment (IPR) of Key Exploitable Results (KER) and stakeholder mapping

T 5.2 Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy

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Executive Summary

This Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results sets out the strategy to effectively promote and exploit BioValue' results. It defines the processes and activities to be implemented and guides stakeholders towards the maximization of the project's impact. The plan provides an overall framework integrating communication, dissemination, and exploitations activities. It starts from the definition of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and a preliminary mapping of the main stakeholder groups. It goes on with the formulation of targeted key messages and the identification of the most suitable dissemination tools and channels, outlining a timeline and envisioning proper dissemination pathways. Additionally, the plan includes monitoring activities to ensure the maximization of content's outreach and engagement, thus assessing the project's impact on target audiences.

Chapter 1 explains the BioValue integrated approach to communication, dissemination, and exploitation, summarizing the project's key objectives.

Chapter 2 focuses on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Starting with the preliminary identification of BioValue's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), it envisions possible exploitations pathways and identifies the main stakeholder groups who can help maximize the project's impact. Afterwards, it articulates the key messages and identifies the communication channels and formats that will be used to spread information linked to the project and promote its results. A focus is put also on the clustering initiatives linked to the projects funded under the "transformative change" call topics, to build synergies and collaboration with a leveraging effect of the project's results, during its duration and potentially after its end.

Subsequently, the chapter describes the integrated way all the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities will be managed, highlighting responsibilities' distribution within the consortium. In the end, the monitoring processes and methodology developed by ICONS are described with reference to the dissemination and communication activities' impacts along with the indicators that will be used to evaluate the audience's engagement with the communication materials.

Chapter 3 is about BioValue exploitation strategy and implements an impact-driven approach to ensure the uptake and sustainability of the project's results. Starting from the preliminary identification of KERs, it describes a framework that includes different exploitation pathways that are strictly link to dissemination activities and builds upon 2 pillars: i) Upscaling and replication of the Biovalue framework; ii) Academic, scientific and research exploitation.

Chapter 4 sums up the previous chapter and draws some preliminary conclusions.

The current document has been drafted based on the general description of the communication and dissemination strategy (Annex I of BioValue Grant Agreement, Part B) and the description of WP5 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (Annex I, Part A). This plan is a "living" document, which will be updated when necessary, during the project's implementation. New approaches and methods will be suggested based on regular review and evaluation of KPIs and engagement rates.

1 Introduction: an integrated approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation

Introduction

BioValue will design and operationalize an analytical framework to assess the transformative change potential of spatial planning for valuing biodiversity and draft useful recommendations for promoting spatial policymaking. BioValue is not just a theoretical project, it is also a demonstration one, as it also applies the analytical framework to three different case studies, representing distinct spatial planning systems and cultures, as well as distinct scales and biodiversity-related situations. The ambition is to suggest improvements to current EU policy practises that can transform how spatial planning and policy affect biodiversity in Europe, leading to innovation in EU policy and financial instruments, territorial organisational structure, and societal engagement.

The project ambitious objectives can be supported through effective and efficient communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy.

The current document (D5.1) will serve as a guide to describe how the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities will take place during the project, presenting targets, tools, methods, and formats that will be used during its implementation.

This document will be complemented by a detailed Stakeholder Mapping Report, that will be released at M14 (D5.4), and the Final Exploitation plan due at M36 (D5.5).

Objectives and approach to dissemination, communication, and exploitation

The BioValue Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plan will consist of three major phases.

Phase I: Spread awareness among the general audience and the targeted key stakeholders. It's relevant at this stage to build and maintain a common project identity. It will help to increase the engagement and awareness in the project's expected results and impacts.

Phase II: Enhance acceptance of innovation: BioValue will focus on disseminating the identified KERs and engaging with the general audience and key targets to demonstrate the benefits of the

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project's innovation. This outreach of contents will be particularly supportive for the uptake of BioValue findings, strategic and operational policy orientations, and new financial instruments. A targeted engagement strategy will be also implemented in line with the mapping of the stakeholders, by defining their role and level of involvement with KERs and value proposition analysis.

Phase III: Guarantee the sustainability and usability of the results: BioValue will create the preconditions to stimulate broader replication of KERs and engage new end-users and wider audiences. These would facilitate the uptake of KERs and ensure continuous dissemination after the project's end.

The impacts and effectiveness of the strategy will be regularly monitored through a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS, based on a set of indicators (which measure the actual stakeholders' engagement (e.g., the Community Engagement Index-CEI).

More details are provided in paragraph 2.8, Monitoring.

The input coming from the monitoring activities would allow to optimize and upgrade the CDE strategy throughout the project. Moreover, the CDE strategy will be rolled out through the implementation of 3 case studies, acting as arenas for transformation with different spatial, territorial, and organisational specificities.

2 Exploitation, dissemination, and Communication

2.1 Preliminary Key Exploitable Results identification and exploitation pathways

The identification of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) represents the set-up for BioValue's exploitation strategy, that will be deployed in 3 consecutive steps along the project:

- Identification of all KERs and assessment of exploitation pathways;
- Design of partners' joint and individual strategies to accelerate biodiversity inclusion in spatial policy and planning processes;
- Implementation of targeted exploitation and dissemination-oriented activities to raise the uptake of the BioValue analytical framework and instruments.

Results are defined as any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge, or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights. A KER is an identified interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream of the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education. Hereafter, the focus of BioValue's exploitation activities will be mainly on KERs.

Results that are objects of exploitation can be products (e.g., platforms, tools) or services (e.g., advisory, consulting services, public services) that can be further used for research, or commercial strategies; or more knowledge-related (methodologies, processes, models, just advancement in knowledge and expertise), which can be leveraged for research and educational purposes, or lay the basis for the development of services.

Results can be individual or joint, whether they have been generated by a single partner or have been jointly developed by two or more partners. Individual results are carried out by single partners and are individually exploited by the single owner outside the project (e.g., a new methodology developed by a partner; specific expertise or knowledge gained). Joint results represent the main assets of the project, usually jointly co-developed by project partners (in this case, the innovative analytical framework), and for which a tight collaboration among partners will be entailed to maximize future exploitation.

Finally, results and their exploitation pathway can come either with a commercial or non-commercial nature, whether they can be brought to the market with profit purposes (i.e., some types of services) or instead for no profit purposes, such as policymaking, research activities and public services. A result can be both commercial and non-commercial if different exploitation pathways are planned. For example, a methodology is by nature non-commercial, but if partners

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plan to launch a new line of advisory services based on it, then its exploitation can also be commercial. Based on KERs and exploitation pathways, different target segments can be defined to customize future activities.

The first step of the BioValue exploitation strategy entails a comprehensive identification and mapping of the project's expected results that have the potential to be further exploited after the project's end. This phase ensures partners' capitalization on research activities and results. The type of results, and the nature of the organizations involved, will drive later in the project the definition of dedicated exploitation strategies, i.e., how outputs will be further used to create an impact beyond BioValue.

To ensure an effective exploitation of the project's results, BioValue exploitation model will be comprehensive in scope and cover all types of results and every possible exploitation pathway. It will foster synergies and cooperation among the project's partners to ensure the uptake and sustainability of the results beyond the project's end

A summary list at the project level is provided below. It will be reviewed and updated during the implementation of the project according to project's developments. The Project's KERs will be published on the Horizon Results Platform.

Table 1 BioValue's Key Exploitable Results

KERs	Type	Owner	Preliminary Exploitation pathways	Target segments
KER1. Analytical framework for biodiversity transformative change in spatial policy and planning	Methodology/ Recommendations	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento.	Upscaling and replication. Further research activities, research projects and publications. Consultancy services.	Polymakers. Public administrations, industries, SMEs and other potential end-users. Research and Academia
KER2. A set of tools for spatial planning transformations	Tools	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ.	Upscaling and replication. Further research activities, research projects and publications. Consultancy services.	Polymakers. Public administrations, industries, SMEs and other potential end-users. Research and Academia

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KER3. Guidelines on the pathways to include these tools in spatial planning	Guidelines	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, CM Mafra, COMUNE TRENTO, CoKnow	Further research activities, research projects and publications. Consultancy services. Know-how.	Policymakers. Associations, Clusters, and membership organizations. Public administrations, industries and other potential end-users. Research and Academia
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From the table above, it is clear that project results will majorly refer to methodology, instruments and recommendations for the advancement in knowledge, with application in spatial planning policymaking and biodiversity mainstreaming.

The development of an analytical framework to assess transformative potential of spatial planning policy and processes is put at the core of the project concept, as an integrated tool that will allow different stakeholders to select the best tools to trigger transformative change and value biodiversity. Additionally other KERs aim at designing and/or developing novel or innovative tools and instruments to be integrated in the analytical framework.

The identified KERs are macro results that refer to the knowledge and activities. Hereafter, we list and describe each KER, detailing some sub-results related to specific partners' activities.

Table 2 KERs description

KER1. Analytical framework for biodiversity transformative change in spatial policy and planning	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
1A - Adaptation and upscaling of existing conceptual and analytical framework for spatial planning, to explore the transformative potential of the three instrumental perspectives.	
1B - Multi-level governance transformative proposals promoting policy-mixes to be replicated across EU Member States.	
KER2. A set of tools for spatial planning transformations	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
2A - Biovalue interactive platform, a tool for sharing data, information and knowledge as well as co-producing new knowledge on spatial planning.	
2B - Collection and selection of innovative tools, methods, methodologies for innovative policy and planning development, including:	
Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (SP&MI)	

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Spatial planning tools that proved to be the most relevant for transformational change on biodiversity, selected from existing platforms and information sharing mechanisms.	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ
Framework for the Ecosystem Services (ES) mapping and assessment in spatial planning decisions to mainstream biodiversity value and to be applied as empirical and operative analysis in the case studies.	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ
Environmental Assessment Instruments (EAI)	
Environmental Assessment Instruments that proved to be the most effective in including and valuing biodiversity.	AAU, IST-ID, UFZ, UniTrento
Causal map tool to improve the identification of causal connections in EAI practice.	AAU, IST-ID, UFZ, UniTrento
Economic and financing economic and financial instruments (E&FIs)	
Economic and Financial Instruments selected to promote biodiversity conservation and enhance ecosystem value during spatial planning process.	UFZ, IST-ID, AAU, UniTrento
Proposal for improving the most promising Economic and Financial Instruments to enhance transformative change for biodiversity in spatial planning	UFZ, IST-ID, AAU, UniTrento

KER3. Guidelines on the pathways to include these tools in spatial planning	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, CM Mafra, COMUNE TRENTO, CoKnow
Working methodologies and projects from the arenas for transformation as guidelines for integrating biodiversity into spatial planning local practices that enable the regeneration of biodiversity:	
Pathways to improving EAI transformative potential based on case study evidence and research activities.	AAU
Organic summary of recommendations for policymakers related to the EU sustainable financing strategy in the context of spatial planning.	UFZ
Provision of economic, social, and environmental data to provide evidence of the biophysical, economic, and socio-cultural impacts of ES.	UniTrento

This description provides a preliminary version of the key exploitable results identified in the BioValue proposal that has been enriched with the information collected from the project's partners by ICONS through the Exploitation Questionnaire (Annex I), distributed after the Exploitation Webinar. Continuous interactions and different rounds of guided interviews,

webinars, and workshops with partners will support the further validation and update of results since the beginning of the project and will follow the project's developments. The identification of the project's results will be followed by a structured collection of the exploitation pathways, that in BioValue will be strictly connected to the dissemination of project's result. Therefore, mainly non-commercial strategies will be considered to make sure results reach the targeted audiences. The joint effort of BioValue's partners will be aimed at ensuring the sustainability and replicability of the project's results in other contexts, for other topics (e.g., climate change) and beyond the project's end. A preliminary view of exploitation pathways can be found in Chapter 3 of this deliverable.

Considering the joint nature of KERs and the ambition of the project to ensure their maximum uptake, results will be generally open and soft IP measures will be adopted to protect scientific publications. Nevertheless, clearly defining IP background and foreground generated, reaching consensus among IP owners on how shared results will be further exploited, and evaluating the proper protection measures and accessibility case by case are crucial steps for designing impactful exploitation strategies; thus, these topics will be carefully addressed in BioValue Final Exploitation Plan (M36).

2.2 Target audiences & key stakeholders

Preliminary Stakeholder Mapping

Within BioValue, stakeholders are individuals, organizations, or businesses with a vested interest in the project and can either affect or be affected by its outputs, application, and performance. Stakeholder mapping is crucial to develop an effective dissemination and engagement strategy and to support a viable exploitation plan. Identifying stakeholders and understanding their needs and priorities allow to effectively plan Dissemination and Communication activities, reach, and involve the right external players in the implementation of the project and its post-action planning and maximize the overall project's return-on-investment (ROI). It will inform the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy execution and provide guidance on the potential targets, partners, channels, and enablers.

BioValue will leverage a stakeholder mapping approach built along 4 distinct steps:

- The identification of different stakeholder groups and the stakeholders in each group according to their "stake" in the project and its results;
- A preliminary description of the stakeholders' profile;
- The development of stakeholders' maps using visual tools;
- The final ranking of stakeholders along a scale of priorities and relevance.

This lays the basis for the development of a targeted engagement and dissemination strategy to leverage KERs towards stakeholders and initiatives.

The current document provides a preliminary mapping of stakeholders. The following steps are under development and will be consolidated at M14 in the Stakeholder Mapping Report (D5.4).

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Step 1: Identifying stakeholders

Considering the definition of “stakeholders” provided above, the process of stakeholders’ identification requires understanding which results (e.g. advancement in knowledge, model, services etc.) the project will deliver, and how partners expect to leverage them post-project (exploitation strategies). Based on KERs (paragraph 2.1), a total of 8 stakeholder groups have been identified.

Table 3 BioValue Stakeholder groups and stakeholders

Stakeholder groups	Stakeholders
Policymakers	Supranational institutions and science-policy bodies at International and European level, including the EU knowledge Center for Biodiversity and Funding Institutions
	National and local governments and associations
Associations, Clusters, and membership organizations	EU projects’ cluster on transformative change
	Clusters, associations, interest groups, membership organizations, and expert panels
	European partnerships and platforms
Industries, SMEs and other potential end-users	Forest and agricultural sector
	Infrastructure sector
	Urban Planning
	Other industries, SMEs and related businesses
	Environment professionals and practitioners
Research and Academia	Research Institutions/Centers and Universities
General public	Local communities: citizens and stakeholders from the case study areas
	The broad European and international public: European citizens and the civil society
Media	Local/International journalists and media

It is important to acknowledge that the identification of stakeholders is based on the KERs’ preliminary exploitation strategy. The current map will be reviewed and updated to reflect the project’s developments.

Step 2: Stakeholder Profiling

This section focuses on providing a short profile for each of the stakeholders’ groups and sub-groups identified, including the following:

- Market of reference or operational context;

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- Geographical area of stakeholders' operation (i.e., national, international etc.);
- Main interests in BioValue's results;
- Examples of key organisations/players.

This analysis was mainly based on desk research of available information, which are all indicated in the footnotes.

Policy Makers

Policy makers operate at different levels and have several supporting internal bodies that contribute to the achievement of their objectives. They play a key role in building a supportive framework to drive biodiversity protection across Europe, setting new global standards for spatial planning, implementing new projects, and supporting national implementation measures. They can therefore influence BioValue by:

- Setting favourable regulatory environments for the development and application of solutions and best practices for mitigating biodiversity loss and accelerating biodiversity-relevant transformative changes in society;
- Providing incentives to the deployment of research projects, innovative models and processes aiming at leveraging transformative change in spatial planning and valuing biodiversity;
- Financing R&D spending in innovative spatial planning actions and biodiversity areas.
- Mainstreaming biodiversity discourse by engaging the broad bundle of stakeholder.

Policy makers can be hierarchically classified into local, national and supranational institutions. EU member state governments operate at local (and provincial and regional level in countries where provinces/regions are present) and national level.

International Level

At the international level, biodiversity is part of the topics addressed by several conventions and major science-policy bodies, under the aegis of the United Nations. The umbrella convention of the United Nation that works for implementing actions is the CBD (Convention on Biological Diversity) and gathers a group of stakeholders that act as decision makers in the context of safeguarding biodiversity and decreasing its loss. Among these science-policy bodies, there are for example **the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystems Services (IPBES) and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)**.

These stakeholders are mainly involved in the purpose of the project because of their role in the decision-making process on biodiversity and the implementation of internationally recognized conventions on the topic that act principally as binding values for the signatory countries. This kind of stakeholders can leverage the knowledge and the instruments developed within the BioValue projects to value biodiversity in decision making and mainstream the messages linked to the need for transformative change in spatial planning.

European Level

At the European level, biodiversity is a target of the policy-making processes, and it is part of the environmental policy-making process. For what concerns spatial planning as well as land management and use, the European Union does not have a direct policy-making role, but has a substantial power, in terms of biodiversity protection, in impacting and influencing national processes through directives and regulations that can drive national legislations toward better practices that take into account biodiversity loss. Moreover, **the European Commission** can impact and influence national spatial planning through agenda and discourse setting by delivering publications, benchmarks, or awards and by addressing the issue in the Country-Specific Recommendations report¹. In 2020 the Commission, together with **the EU knowledge Center for Biodiversity** and in partnership with the Belgian Biodiversity Platform has launched the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030². The Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity is a European Commission initiative on better knowledge management for policymaking on biodiversity. It aims at enhancing the knowledge base, facilitate its sharing and foster cross-sectorial policy dialogue for EU policy making in biodiversity and related fields.

Also, specific **Directorates** are relevant for BioValue's themes, such as the DG ENV; DG Research & Innovation; DG AGRI MEPs, as well as **Executive Agencies** such as the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA).

Finally, another aspect that makes European Institutions fundamental stakeholders for BioValue project is the financial support they deliver. A range of opportunities for financing biodiversity projects at EU level, includes the European Funds for Structural Investment (ESIF), LIFE Programme and Horizon EU.³

National and local governments and associations

In terms of biodiversity, national governments represent fundamental stakeholders in BioValue project, since they oversee implementing biodiversity-related regulations, recommendations and projects coming from the European or international levels projects. The significance of national governments has two implications: on one side its indigenous nature and on the other side the responsibility for spatial planning and management. Within national governments, there are different authorities and ministries that are specific stakeholders for the purposes of Biovalue, such as the Regional Nature Conservation authority, the Ministry of Environment, the Ministry of Forestry, and the Ministry of Regional Planning, that is liable for spatial planning/managing and land use in partnership with the Ministry or department of Agriculture.

These stakeholders are directly involved in reaching Biovalue's goals at a national level across Europe, as they are responsible for the protection of biodiversity in relations to spatial planning and land use and they also manage the economic and financial instruments that are set to reach Biovalue's purposes.

The importance of the subnational authorities is especially determinant because of their role in mainstreaming biodiversity at the broader public and the technical bodies of which they are

¹ Available at: <https://cor.europa.eu/en/engage/studies/Documents/Spatial-planning-new-urban-agenda.pdf>

² Available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/commission-launches-new-mechanisms-strengthened-eu-biodiversity-governance-2021-12-15_en

³ Available at: <https://cor.europa.eu/en/engage/studies/Documents/Financing%20biodiversity%20action.pdf>

composed. The subnational authorities are especially important for their proximity to indigenous and local communities, they can therefore be able to promote more tailored measures and also to inform and mainstream biodiversity to the general public in a more proximate manner. Municipalities intended as basic administrative divisions, are major stakeholders since they are the ones in charge of addressing biodiversity loss and spatial planning at the local level. Given their role, they can leverage the experience gained by the other municipalities acting as arenas for transformation within BioValue project and uptake and replicate BioValue's framework and tools.

In the same way, associations representing the interests of local and regional governments are important stakeholders in the project, because on the one hand they represent local interests to be considered when talking about spatial planning decision making, on the other they mainstream capillary biodiversity value reaching local authorities and citizens. Some examples are **ICLEI (Local Governments for Sustainability)**, **EUROCITIES** and **UCLG (United Cities and Local Governments)**.

Associations, Clusters, and membership organizations

Associations, clusters, and membership organizations linked to BioValue's goals operate at a national, regional, and European level and include collaborative platforms and networks with the purpose of gathering available knowledge and bringing innovative solutions forward. Some of their specific group interests are to promote biodiversity protection policies, implementing effective spatial planning recommendations and developing good practices in relation to biodiversity and spatial planning.

EU projects' cluster on transformative change

European projects focusing on biodiversity have proliferated and their objectives are mainly based on tighter collaborations enhancing the development of innovative solutions that seek to safeguard biodiversity and the reversal of ecosystems degradation, in accordance with the goals of EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030.

In particular, BioValue project has a tight link to the projects funded under the "transformative change" call topics. The projects that are currently funded are: **CLEVER, BAMBOO, BIONEXT, SUSTAIN, BIOTRAILS, RAINFOREST, TC4BE, TRANSPATH, BIOTraCes and PLANET4B** (see paragraph 2.6). The interest of these projects is to build a research and innovation cluster aiming to maximise the impact and exploitation of results of the projects and facilitate feedback to policy. Synergies and collaboration among these EU funded projects allow for the construction of a systematic scientific framework for biodiversity and spatial planning, leveraging the knowledge developed within the single projects and amplifying the potential impact of the results on the society. Moreover, further research projects and activities can be carried out to address relevant issues for the society and existing knowledge gaps.

Clusters, associations, interest groups, membership organizations and expert panels

Clusters are groups of associations, businesses and organizations joining forces in addressing environmentally challenging questions. They share knowledge, expertise, and technical know-how in the context of biodiversity, spatial planning and other themes that are relevant in BioValue project's uptake. Clusters prove to be particularly constructive due to their capacity of reaching as many stakeholders as possible and be therefore fundamental in the dissemination process. A

couple of examples of existing clusters in the context of biodiversity and social planning are the ESA Biodiversity Science Cluster that fosters international collaboration on Biodiversity and the European online hub for industry clusters that deals also with biodiversity-related aspects of the economy.

Some other stakeholders in the BioValue project are:

- **Associations** helping biodiversity protection through the provision of knowledge and financing instruments are the Association for Biodiversity Conservation, the World Wildlife Fund, and the Wildlife Conservation Society;
- **Interest groups** dealing with environmental and biodiversity protection, such as the CEEweb for biodiversity and Friends for Earth Europe;
- **Membership organizations** that are mainly composed of citizens and smaller organizations that are brought together with the scope of raising awareness within institutions such as EEB (European Environmental Bureau).

Finally, international expert panels on the main project's topics can leverage the knowledge, recommendations and tools developed within the BioValue project and exploit them to advance students' education and professionals' practices. Some examples of expert panels on spatial planning are the **Association of European Schools of Planning, the Association of Collegiate Schools of Planning and the International Urban Development Association.**

European partnerships and platforms

European partnerships bring public and private partners together and play an important role in addressing some of the Europe's most pressing challenges through concerted research and innovation initiatives. These partnerships operate at an EU regional level and act as permanent platforms for knowledge sharing, mutual exchange, policy learning and cooperation. Some of their interests include finding innovative solutions to avoid biodiversity loss through transformative change. Examples of these partnerships and platforms are: **Biodiversa+, Oppla, NetworkNature, the EU Biodiversity Platform, EU B@B, the Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity and ESPON- European Spatial Planning Observatory Network.**

The synergies will allow to make options available on how to implement and mainstream, in practice, biodiversity into spatial policy and planning, considering BioValue results.

Industries, SMEs, and other potential end-users

Different business sectors, that can be considered as "land-consuming" and biodiversity harming, are part of the BioValue's groups of stakeholders. These stakeholders include entities such as private businesses, SMEs and start-ups that operate at all geographical levels and can be linked to the project because of their interest in its results. Indeed, they can integrate the tools and recommendations produced by the BioValue project in their processes, developing sustainable spatial planning decision-making and practices as well as mainstreaming biodiversity value by engaging the numerous stakeholders. Moreover, businesses are also eager to collaborate with policymakers in implementing effective land use and spatial planning projects⁴, since a properly implemented strategy can promote investments, development, and improvement of the quality of

⁴ World Business Council for Sustainable Development; Effective Biodiversity and Ecosystem policy and regulation: Business input to the COP10 of the Convention on Biological Diversity; October 2010

life. The actors in the field of business, industries and SMEs can be classified according to their sectoral interest in the project, such as Agricultural and Forest sector, Infrastructure sector, Urban Planning and others.

Agricultural and Forest sector

The conversion of forests to alternative land uses, such as agriculture, is considered a leading driver of biodiversity loss⁵. Industries, SMEs and other related businesses operating in the primary sector are therefore an active part in the use of land and its conversion and they can therefore be considered as stakeholders that are impacted by the outcomes of the project and can contribute to effective and sustainable land use. In particular, the global food system involves the production of food for 8 billion people in the world involving intensive agricultural activities that, according to researchers, accounts for around half of the planet's habitable land⁶. The food system does not only impact biodiversity loss, but also is impacted by it, the UN Organization for Food and Agriculture has highlighted the threat that biodiversity loss has on food security. Agricultural industries, businesses and SMEs are therefore interested in the project's results and can be beneficially impacted by the transformative potential of effective design and implementation of land use planning. They can leverage the new knowledge and instruments developed and validated within the arenas for transformation, sustaining their uptake and replication.

Infrastructure sector

Infrastructures comprise a wide range of "land-consuming" initiatives, like transportation lines, energy supplies and communications connectivity. They are all fundamental sectors, not only for their potentially high employment rates, but also for their importance in the societal development as explicitly cited in the UN Sustainable Development Goal number 9. The developmental path of the infrastructure sector is impacting and will impact biodiversity in terms of environmental damage, for this purpose the European Commission has introduced the concept of green infrastructure with the clear scope of protecting biodiversity through nature-based solutions in the infrastructure sector.^{7,8} Stakeholders in this group, such as the Green infrastructure (GI) network, can act as a stakeholder in BioValue since they can leverage the knowledge and experience gained thanks to the project, mainstream the best practices and tools developed within the arenas for transformations and sustain replication.

Urban planning

Landscape planning-related industries and businesses are representatives of the phenomenon of urbanization, that is considered among the drivers of biodiversity loss, as BioValue points out. They represent a perfect platform for linking biodiversity with spatial planning and land use practices

⁵ Available at: <https://cpree.princeton.edu/land-use-change-and-biodiversity#:~:text=The%2odegradation%2oand%2oconversion%2oof,by%2othe%2olooming%2oclimate%2ocrisis>.

⁶ Available at: <https://www.zurich.com/en/media/magazine/2021/food-for-thought-what-biodiversity-means-to-you#:~:text=How%2odoes%2oagriculture%2oaffected%2obiodiversity,of%2oland%2oof%2oits%2obiodiversity>.

⁷ Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal9>

⁸ Available at: <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/green-infrastructure>

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that take into consideration environmental assessment plans. Landscape and urban planning are, therefore, activities that have the potential to pursue biodiversity conservation. These stakeholders, that include architects and designers' firms, can coordinate the theoretical biodiversity values with an actual application of biodiversity-related policies. Therefore, they can leverage the project's results by including the new knowledge and processes in their work practices, following the proposed recommendations, and replicating the BioValue analytical framework. This will allow them to develop new tools, services and consultancy activities to be included in their portfolio.

Other industries, SMEs and related businesses

Any other industries, SMEs, start-ups, and related business operating in different sectors and geographical areas, that are interested in implementing and replicating BioValue's framework and tools will be considered as stakeholders in the exploitation of project's results.

Environment professionals and practitioners

Environment professionals and practitioners investigate, address, and advise on a variety of environment and resource management issues, including the development and implementation of policies and actions that reduce the impacts of human activities and industrial processes on the environment. This category includes environmental managers, environmental engineers, environmental lawyers, spatial planners as well as ecosystem and environmental services providers. They can use BioValue results to develop new decision-making processes and practices to value biodiversity within the organizations they work in or propose new services and models in their consultancy activities for relevant industrial sectors, ensuring compliance with EU recommendations and regulations and supporting the adoption of best practices.

Research & Academia

Research Institutions operate at different levels and are normally funded to advance science, pioneer new technologies and power new markets and industries. Beyond BioValue partners, key organizations can be of fundamental importance in the development of research and knowledge in the field of spatial planning and biodiversity. Moreover, they can contribute to the distribution of scientific research to the public and act as consultancy partners for private businesses in the field of spatial planning sustainable solutions and sustain the policy-making process in terms of biodiversity protection. Additionally, they can further exploit the project scientific results in future R&I initiatives, designing new specific research activities or developing new research lines for the incorporation of biodiversity as value for society and in spatial planning. Finally, they can also undertake research activities and projects to uptake and replicate BioValue's analytical framework and tools for transformative change within other relevant topics, such as climate change.

These stakeholders include:

- **Universities and Research Institutes** operating in different areas that are impacted by BioValue's results, such as biodiversity, environment, landscape design and spatial planning, sustainable architecture, and socioeconomics.

2.1 Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

- **Research groups** that gather private and public research institutions, universities, and companies to collaborate on common research topics, integrating competencies and knowledge.
- **The R&D departments of private businesses and firms**, complementing the scientific community with a focus on privately- funded research developments.

General Public

The general public is a direct target of BioValue, as the project presents a series of benefits and opportunities to the economy, the environment, and the citizens themselves, in terms of security of food, housing and access to biodiversity. The role that the general public plays in BioValue is fundamental since they are the target of engagement initiatives in the context of the project and therefore, they are to be considered as active players.

This stakeholders' groups are considered according to the geographical proximity to the three arenas for transformation, that are in Mafra Municipality (Portugal), in the Mecklenburg-Vorpommern Federal State (Germany) and in the Trento Municipality (Italy). Obviously, the public that falls within the three areas has direct and short-term interests in the project's results, in terms of their application and upscale. This stakeholders' group is represented by the local communities, that is to say case-studies' actors, citizens and stakeholders at large.

The rest of the public across Europe, ranging from citizens and the civil society, can leverage the knowledge and experience developed within the arenas for transformation, sustain the mainstreaming of BioValue main messages and promote the replication of the solutions in different contexts.

Media

There is a long-standing debate about the role of media as a target or multiplier of information. The BioValue consortium believes in the latter and considers media as a platform to reach the targeted stakeholders profiled in this report (rather than a target itself). Mainstream media are considered in the context of BioValue of multipliers of the key messages of the project as well as one of the means to achieve the general public, a considerable stakeholder of the project.

2.3 Key messages at general and stakeholder level

The challenge of reaching such a variety of audiences and targets entails the need to create a series of key messages that communicate BioValue core objectives. Blending specific keywords, messages and target audiences ensures the likelihood for the project to resonate with each audience and to generate meaningful impact.

The following tables provide an overview of the BioValue key messages:

Table 4: Key Messages at the project level

BioValue will leverage transformative change in spatial planning to promote biodiversity
BioValue will value biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions

The following table provides an overview of the BioValue's key messages.

Table 5 Key messages at target level

Target	Key Message	Tagline
Industry and other potential end-users	Thanks to BioValue's transformative approach, industries and other end-users can enhance biodiversity value in spatial planning, while paving the way for new business opportunities and further development.	A NEW APPROACH FOR NEW BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES
Researchers and academia	Academia can benefit from advancements in knowledge about transformative change tools brought by BioValue and fuel further research projects and collaborations.	NEW KNOWLEDGE FOR NEW RESEARCH INITIATIVES
	BioValue will prompt R&I initiatives, new R&D lines aimed at improving and further develop the incorporation of biodiversity in spatial planning as a value for society.	
Policymakers and the EC Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD)	BioValue will analyse and develop recommendations on existing regulations and strategies for EU policy officers, national local governments, local governments, and representative associations.	NEW RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BETTER POLICY
Local communities, citizens and stakeholders at large	BioValue will actively contribute to the ongoing dialogue, increase awareness, raise interest, and stimulate engagement on transformative change in spatial planning enhancing biodiversity.	BIODIVERSITY NEEDS EVERYONE'S ENGAGEMENT
The broad European and international public	BioValue support transformative actions for enhancing biodiversity that will have social, environmental, economic positive impacts and benefits for environment and society.	BIODIVERSITY IS GOOD FOR EVERYONE

The project will develop dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy articulated upon the following stages: Engage, Produce, Share and Exchange.

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Figure 1 A tailored approach to Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Dissemination and Communication play a fundamental role in the “Share”, “Exchange” and “Engage” stages. The project dissemination makes the project’s results available to the scientific community, policymakers, and industry. Its ultimate scope is to facilitate the scientific reuse of the results to generate long term scientific impact. Communication activities, on the other hand, increase the public visibility of the project and its results. It relies on non-technical language to trigger public interest in the project topic and to showcase the benefits BioValue will bring into people’s lives in the long term.

Table 6 Difference between dissemination and communication

	Dissemination	Communication
Objectives	Public disclosure of scientific and technical results	Promotion of the project and its results
Audience	Professional target groups, such as scientific communities, industry stakeholders, policymakers, etc.	The general public, including EU citizens, civil society
Tone of voice	Scientific/technical language	Non-specialized/plain language
Channels	Peer-review journals, scientific conferences, sector events, the web, newsletters etc.	The web, social networks, newspapers, TV channels, radio etc.

Aligned and coordinated with communication and dissemination activities, exploitation activities will aim at preparing the playground for the exploitation of scientific results and technological solutions after the end of the project.

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BioValue will also explore the Horizon Results Booster services to reinforce cooperation with the other EU projects funded under the “transformative change” call topics and consider the possibility to design a joint dissemination and communication portfolio.

The following table shows how each category identified through the stakeholder mapping exercise will be addressed by the project dissemination and communication. Depending on stakeholders’ needs, dissemination content will be tailored and relayed through effective and impactful formats and channels.

Table 7 D&C tailored to BioValue stakeholders

Stakeholders	Dissemination formats	Communication channels	How D&C supports exploitation
Industry and other potential end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Info-packs and factsheets • Technical brochure • Webinars and local workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media channels (LinkedIn) 	Targeted dissemination materials will be strategically planned to reach environmental managers, spatial planners, practitioners, professionals; ecosystem and environmental services providers; financial institutions, SMEs and start-ups. Dissemination and communication activities will facilitate engagement and participation to collect inputs during the project phases and allow for future upscale and replication of BioValue framework and tools.
Researchers and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Participation in symposia • Posters/ speeches • Networking with experts of fellow projects/initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) • Sister project’s website and social media • Scientific journals 	Scientific papers produced by BioValue will provide scientific evidence of the transformative change capability of spatial planning to promote biodiversity. Research dissemination activities will allow research centres and universities to exploit the new knowledge for further research activities and projects.
Policymakers and the EC Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBd)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentations at EU premises and EU Parliament • Discussion events • Policy briefs and recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sister project’s website and social media • Website • Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) 	Policymakers will be presented the framework developed by BioValue as an integrated approach to transformative change in spatial planning with the goal to promote biodiversity. Evidence gathered by the project on the transformative potential of the different instruments may be used as a base for elaborating policies which will

			leverage spatial planning to value biodiversity. Cooperation with the EC Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD) will be established to create synergies and ensure efficient and well-targeted dialogue and dissemination.
Local communities, citizens, and stakeholders at large	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media animation and campaigns • Public workshops • Community-led events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn. Instagram to be evaluated) • Media Multipliers 	Targeted dissemination and communication activities will be aimed at increasing awareness, raising interest, and stimulating engagement to ensure the uptake and suitability of the BioValue results among case studies and stakeholders. Dissemination and communication activities will help build capacity, maximise knowledge transfer and communication among local actors and stakeholders.
The broad European and international public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sector events (discussion table) • Project presentation • Workshop • Production of a policy and recommendations • Project videos • Press and news releases • Journalistic articles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn. Instagram to be evaluated) • Media Multipliers • Newsletter 	Targeted communication and dissemination strategies will be elaborated to address local and EU citizens to facilitate transfer of key messages. Media outlets and journalists (at EU and local level) will be engaged through a media kit as well as via regular information about the project, its results, and impacts. Direct engagement with NGOs and CSOs, both representing the interests of citizens and the civil society in addressing social, environmental, and political issues, will be established at both EU and national/local level.

2.4 Dissemination and Communication Channels

Table 8 Dissemination and Communication channels at the target level

Channel	Description	Target
Website	The project website will be used to showcase details about the project, its objectives, challenges, and results. It will act as the primary communication channel between the consortium and BioValue target audiences. It will also facilitate exchange with stakeholders.	All
Social networks (Twitter and LinkedIn)	These will actively engage with the online community of the project's followers by informing them about the	All

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Instagram to be evaluated)	progress made by BioValue and by inviting them to participate in a dialogue on the different topics/issues addressed by the project.	
Newsletter	It is released on a six-months basis to inform about the progress made by the project. It collects key events, journalistic articles, news or press releases realized within the project. Sister projects, partnerships and clusters will find a space in the BioValue newsletter.	All (except general public)
Media multipliers	These are external platforms that republish the journalistic articles, news, and press releases written by BioValue.	All
News and press releases	They can be used to inform the community about the main project achievements and milestones and promote project events and progress. They can also focus on the specific issues of public relevance.	Academia, Research Centers; Experts and other players in EU projects. Policy makers.
Events	These come in the form of 1) physical and virtual workshops, including webinars, to facilitate stakeholder integration; 2) joint organisation of conferences or workshops to engage with the other projects funded under the "transformative change" call topics.	All (except general public)

Website

The project website represents the main communication and dissemination channel. It encompasses all the BioValue main themes as well as more in-depth information and resources as the project unfolds. The website is built with a dialogical nature, to introduce the BioValue main concepts and make them understandable to the wide public. It is meant to provide regular news items about the project and the three arenas for transformation. The BioValue website was released in a first version in October 2022 (M4) that included a landing page and the possibilities to subscribe to the project's newsletter. A second version will be realised at the end December 2022 (M6), featuring additional pages and information. The two-step approach was adopted to ensure an online presence since M4, in compliance with the Grant Agreement. The website is available at biovalue-horizon.eu.

BioValue leverages transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructures development, to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions.

Funded by the European Union

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Federal State, Germany

What does it mean?

Transformative change implies a fundamental system-wide reorganization of how spatial planning processes are governed, including shifts in behavioural, social, cultural, economic, institutional, technical, and technological dimensions, and underpinning paradigms, goals, and values.

How does it work?

BioValue explores transformative change in **three Arenas for Transformation**, representing distinct spatial planning systems and cultures, as well as distinct scales and biodiversity-related situations.

1

Rewetting Peatlands and reforestation under the climate initiative

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
Federal State
Germany

Funded by the European Union

2
Municipal spatial
planning
Mafra
Municipality
Portugal

3
Urban planning
Trento
Municipality
Italy

Do you want to be part of the
transformative change?

[Keep me updated](#)

 BioValue

Biodiversity value in spatial policy and planning
leveraging multi-level and transformative change

info@biovalue-horizon.eu

[Twitter](#) [Facebook](#) [LinkedIn](#)

[Privacy policy](#)
[Quality of content](#)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101060790

Figure 2 BioValue homepage

Funded by the European Union

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The project website will be useful for the following purposes:

- to cross-link it with external platforms, relevant initiatives, partnerships, and sister projects;
- to provide links to joint workshop and webinar and practical information about training and other stakeholder engagement activities promoted by the project;
- to be informed about the project's activities and be targeted by its dissemination initiatives using the newsletter's registration form.

The website is structured to encourage navigation across sections and topics. It consists of static pages that will be updated regularly during the project. All the contents published on the website are accessible to all viewers with no restrictions.

Accountability	<p>The website is developed and managed by ICONS, with input and feedback from IST-ID and all the partners. Input and co-operation from IST-ID and the rest of the BioValue partnership will be encouraged during the project duration.</p> <p>To comply with General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the Data Controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by registered users upon online registration.</p>
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Social Networks

Dedicated social networks will be activated to promote widely the project, its objectives, and results.

BioValue have already a social media presence on Twitter and LinkedIn which will be used with different tone of voices and to reach different audiences. While Twitter's content will be constantly up to date and follow the European Commission accounts, clustering projects and the general public, LinkedIn company page are mainly dedicated to a professional audience. Both social media channels will be supported by a social media strategy aimed to maintain a weekly editorial plan with daily interactions with all users.

Twitter channel (https://twitter.com/biovalue_eu) was created in October 2022 and will be maintained all throughout the duration of the project. It will produce regular tweets to get the public's attention regarding BioValue' main results: public deliverables, scientific publications, details, and follow-up news about the progress made by the project, and facts worth bringing up to attract the targeted online community's attention.

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Figure 3 BioValue on social media – Twitter homepage

The LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/89248300/admin/>) was opened in October 2022 as well. It will be maintained throughout the duration of the project. The project's communication effort will be devoted to ensuring that the project gains good visibility in the LinkedIn groups used by the stakeholders' community. BioValue will produce regular posts to keep the online communities interested and informed about its progress and activities, and its upcoming events. These channels will enable our project to establish early on an engaging relationship with groups and LinkedIn pages.

Funded by the European Union

Figure 4 BioValue on social media – LinkedIn homepage

The consortium will evaluate the activation of an Instagram account. Instagram requires the constant publication of high-quality and original images and short videos to ensure the ongoing animation of the feed and maximize the reached audience. Therefore, the decision will be evaluated against the amount and quality of contents, especially images, collected from the partners and the ones created by the project. The channel could be useful to communicate insights, main concepts and examples related to transformative change in spatial planning and biodiversity to the general public and to strengthen the relationship with the other clustering projects.

In any case, BioValue presence on social media will boost the outreach of our project’s communication and dissemination activities, as it will reach a larger audience through other conventional project channels.

Furthermore, the members of the BioValue consortium are encouraged to follow existing LinkedIn groups regularly and post news (produced by the project) and facts worth bringing to the attention of these groups. These LinkedIn groups will be carefully chosen to have in mind the BioValue stakeholder audience.

The project has set an official hashtag, **#biovalueEU**, to track the impact of the conversation about it.

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Figure 5 BioValue on social media - Hashtag

The hashtag will be used to monitor posts about BioValue and to gather quantitative and qualitative impact data.

Accountability	<p>ICONS will be responsible for the core social media activities, like setting up the accounts, posting following existing social media channels and monitoring outreach.</p> <p>The consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by joining the community of BioValue Twitter and LinkedIn followers. They can retweet and repost our content from their organizations' channels and use the #biovalueEU hashtag.</p>
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Newsletter

A project newsletter will be developed and issued every six months and delivered online to all the people who will register to the BioValue website to follow the project.

Funded by the European Union

Newsletters are particularly effective to engage the professional community. Industries, research stakeholders and policymakers will use the newsletter to be informed about the progress made by the project. The project newsletter is also a valid tool to encourage cooperation with sister projects, partnerships, and sector clusters through cross-fertilization initiatives and cross-linkages. It will be written in English, in HTML format.

Accountability	ICONS will collect content, program the newsletter and will take care of dispatching it to the online registered users. All project partners are encouraged to send in relevant news and events to be included in the newsletter.
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Multipliers

External media multipliers will be used to disseminate contents of general interest produced by BioValue.

These tools are external platforms that have syndication agreements with ICONS. The most used multipliers are EU Agenda, Science Daily, AlphaGalileo, and Phys.org. Additional channels with a focus on the topics covered by BioValue will also be included in the project distribution list. Where appropriate, the IST-ID communication officer will be informed about the BioValue production and asked to support the distribution of our materials via their online channels.

Products to be distributed will include journalistic articles, press and news releases, and audiovisuals (T5.5) on BioValue.

The rest of the BioValue consortium is encouraged to republish the project's press and news releases via their networks. For monitoring purposes, the partners will have to inform ICONS once they re-distribute the abovementioned materials.

All communication materials produced by the project will be regularly monitored to quantify their outreach and understand the interactions and the level of engagement of news, press releases and journalistic articles.

Accountability	ICONS will be responsible for distributing the news and press releases and journalistic articles to external news multipliers. The consortium partners are encouraged to re-distribute these materials within their networks. Monitoring will measure the outreach of BioValue's communication channels.
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2.5 Dissemination & Communication materials and formats

Table 9 Dissemination and communication material and formats

Material/Format	Description	Target
Communication Kit	The BioValue communication kit will include a flyer and a presentation video, besides the project's logo, brandbook,	Partners

	and website. Communication materials will be distributed both online (as downloadable materials on the website), and offline (to be displayed at the arenas for transformation, exhibitions and external events attended by the partners). The materials' design will be consistent with the project's visual identity. The kit will be ready in February 2023 (M8).	
Scientific publications	Technical and academic partners will produce scientific articles and papers to be published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. Such scientific publications will present cutting-edge results from BioValue.	Academia, RTOs, researchers, scientific community, and technical experts
Info-packs	Info-packs and factsheets will be exploitation-oriented and focus on the transformative change's approaches tested by BioValue in the arenas for transformation. They will be distributed specifically to companies and value chains to show the way for new business opportunities and further development.	Industries and other potential end users
Technical brochure	The BioValue technical brochure will feature the project's key achievements, best practices, lessons learned and recommendations to hand over to the industry and other end users. ICONS will design the layout while partners will provide the technical content. It will come in electronic and printable formats during the last phases of the project.	Industries and other potential end users
Policy briefs	Evidence-based policy briefs will be produced to disseminate strategic and operational recommendations. In this process BioValue also relies on the insights provided by the commission liaison officer in identifying key-targets and key moments to maximise the impact.	Experts and other players in EU projects. Policy makers Financing bodies

Communication Kit

The communication Kit will be produced by February 2022 (M8), providing partners with the professional quality material necessary to promote the project. This will include a flyer and a presentation video, besides the project's logo, brand book and templates that have already been released at M4. Moreover, a press release has been published and distributed in October 2022,

announcing the start of the project and describing its main goals. The short presentation video in English will show and explain the BioValue' concept and its impacts on non-technical audiences.

The resources from the communication kit will support the project communication by allowing the BioValue partners to use them to engage with stakeholders, particularly when participating in events. It will contain all the main information stakeholders need to know regarding the project. The materials will follow the project visual identity developed in October 2022 (M4). All visual materials will be available in electronic format for download.

Accountability	ICONS will oversee the development and the design of the materials by February 2023 (M8). Partner will provide any further information that may be necessary for the development of the kit.
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Scientific publications

The project is expected to generate scientific results worth to be disseminated in scientific conferences and published in high-ranked peer-reviewed scientific journals.

BioValue papers will feature the most interesting findings sought out by the academic and research partners within the project. Possibilities to publish in open access mode will be investigated in the consortium. News about the release of BioValue' scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the project website and social media channels.

Accountability	Research and academic partners will be the main responsible for the release and publishing of these actions. ICONS will keep track of all the scientific publications made by these partners within the project. Moreover, ICONS will promote such publications via the project website and social media.
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Info-packs

Info packs and factsheets come in the form of fact- and info- sheets or synthetic reports. These are specifically designed for the professional community to learn about technical insights, solutions and tools developed by BioValue.

They allow our communication team to package technical achievements and findings into a visually attractive and easy-to-access document. The specific contents will be taken from the public deliverables and scientific publications produced by the project.

Their format makes them particularly suitable to be distributed at scientific and technical events. Moreover, they will also be made available for download from the project website and will be actively distributed to key stakeholders' groups interested in being up to date on project results.

Accountability	ICONS will oversee the development and the graphic design of the info packs and factsheets. They will liaise with technical partners to collect content to be featured in such resources. When the content
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of the info pack and factsheet will be particularly technical, BioValue partners or the coordinator will be asked to draft the specific content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and layout.

Technical brochure

The BioValue technical brochure will feature the project's key achievements, best practices, lessons learned, and recommendations based on evidence gathered from the different stages of the project and from the three arenas form transformation.

It will be issued towards the end of the project, when the BioValue partnership will be in the position to draw some conclusions from the project, worth to be passed industries and other end users for replications.

ICONS will design the layout while partners will provide the technical content. It will come in electronic and printable formats.

Accountability

ICONS will oversee the development and the graphic design of the technical brochure. They will liaise with technical partners to collect content to be presented. If some information needs to be particularly technical, partners or the coordinator will be asked to contribute to the specific content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and layout.

Policy briefs

BioValue policy briefs will be produced to disseminate strategic and operational recommendations among EU policy makers, also through presentations at EU premises and EU Parliament, and other national and local policy makers.

They will draw some key messages from the evidence collected throughout the project and from the three arenas for transformations.

ICONS will design the layout while partners will provide the technical information and key messages to be delivered. It will come in electronic and printable formats.

Accountability

ICONS will oversee the development and the graphic design of the policy briefs. They will liaise with technical partners to collect content to be featured in such resources. When the content of the policy briefs will be particularly technical, BioValue partners or the coordinator will be asked to draft the specific content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and layout.

Editorial content

Table 10 Dissemination and communication material and formats

Editorial content	Description	Target
Journalistic articles	Independent articles and interviews to project's experts and external stakeholders will be produced by professional journalists and distributed to online media, thematic portals, and other information outlets.	All
Press and news releases	They can be used to inform the community about the main project achievements and milestones and promote project events and progress.	All
Audio-visual products	Audio-visuals in different formats will be produced to facilitate transfer of BioValue's key messages. Two videos will be produced over the project, a presentation video (M8) and a final one (M36). Several short videos and interviews will be realized to be featured on social media channels. Their format will be suitable for online distribution, although they will also be used to present the project at sector events.	All

Journalist articles

Independent journalistic articles and interviews will be written by professional journalists. They will cover topics linked to BioValue from a perspective that is suitable to reach through to a wide range of audiences, without requiring a technical background

They will be published via the project website. Moreover, they will be distributed to the public at a European and global level using different multipliers or media platforms, namely EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo, Science daily, Phys.org, and other platforms which will be indicated as suitable for the project distribution.

When journalistic articles will be released, they will also be promoted through the available social media channels. When deemed relevant for the community of followers, content from news releases and project updates will feed into the project's social media channels.

Journalistic articles are meant to inform and stimulate interest among the public about the topics covered by the project. It will serve to present BioValue's results to a laymen audience, since the project aims at spreading awareness on biodiversity at different levels and changing behaviours of the single persons as long as institutions' decisions. Journalistic articles and project interviews can

raise public awareness of the project's key ideas and ultimately contribute to social acceptance of its results.

Accountability	The editorial production will be discussed by ICONS with IST-ID. Contents will originate either from external sources collected by journalists (during their investigation) or directly from the BioValue project. ICONS will take care of the distribution.
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Press and news releases

BioValue press and news releases are meant to draw the stakeholders' and the public's attention towards the project, the progress made, and the results achieved.

Press releases are official statement that are prepared for and delivered to members of the news media for making a newsworthy announcement or providing information about a specific event. They are particularly effective when it comes to communicating the project's main achievements and key milestones, like the release of a scientific paper or a technical deliverable. Key targets is the professional audience, who do not necessarily have specific background and knowledge related to the project (e.g. journalists, sector portals, other projects).

News releases, on the other hand, have a more informal structure and they use a plain language as they are easily read by the public. They are usually published on the project website to communicate news about the project, its features and its work which are all worth bring to the attention of the BioValue community despite not being "breaking news". A news release will be produced, for example, to give explanation of an innovative concept developed by the project or on background information to a project activity. News releases are particularly effective when informing of the participation of some members of the BioValue partnership to external events to present their latest project findings or achievement.

Both the press releases and the news releases will be published on the project website and, whenever the content is particularly relevant, they'll be distributed to external online resources and news multipliers (like Eu Agenda, AlphaGalileo, Science Daily, Phys.org).

They will be distributed to external media channels described under "media multipliers". This will be done to increase the visibility of the project's concrete actions taking up, sharing and re-publishing some of the project's content and cascading them down to the existing audience.

ICONS will be collecting and monitoring on a six-months basis all publications released by partners through a dedicated template.

Accountability	ICONS will be responsible for producing and distributing press and news releases on behalf of BioValue. All the members of the consortium will flag up to ICONS interesting aspects worth covering by press or news releases, by providing them with the necessary details and background information. ICONS will draft them and take care of their distribution.
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	Once they are ready, the other members of the consortium will be encouraged to further distribute them through their portals, newsletters, or other appropriate channels.
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Audio-visual products

BioValue videos will aim at communicating the project in an easy and more engaging way. They can be developed in different formats (infographics and animation, scribing technique, real footage, stock images, etc.) according to the audience, the targets, and the channels to be used for distribution.

The first BioValue presentation video will be part of the communication kit and released at the beginning of the project (D 5.2, M8). It will focus on the general concept and objectives of the project. The second video will be produced towards the end of the project to present the project results and their impact. Moreover, four short video interviews with experts and external stakeholders will be produced throughout the lifetime of the project, as long as short video clips for social media animation.

Videos are intended to facilitate the information transfer of more complex content to a wide audience. The videos will be widely promoted and distributed via social media, the project website, other sector-related communication portals and communication platforms.

Accountability	ICONS will oversee the production, development, and distribution of the videos. The format and content to be featured in the video will be preliminarily discussed with IST-ID. Inputs from BioValue coordinator and other partners will be asked to integrate the content.
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2.6 Clustering, synergies, and events attendance

BioValue partners will participate in networking and clustering events to raise the project's visibility within the stakeholder community.

First of all, it will join forces with sister EU funded projects, sector partnerships and initiatives. All the project partners will continuously collaborate to create synergies and cooperate with other projects and initiatives of interest that might provide significant leveraging effect, including Horizon Europe activities such as the European Partnerships and Missions. In particular, collaboration will be established between the projects funded under the "transformative change" call topics HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-15, HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-16, HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-17, HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-21, HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-08, HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-09 to build a research and innovation cluster aiming to maximise the impact and exploitation of results of the projects, and facilitate feedback to policy. To date, the projects funded under these topics are:

The projects that are currently funded are:

- **CLEVER** project aims at identifying new leverage points for sustainable transformation. Applying a novel holistic approach, the project will quantify biodiversity and other impacts of trade in major raw and processed non-food biomass value chains.
- **BAMBOO** project develops models to quantify biodiversity impacts. It provides a comprehensive and detailed knowledge of the effects of biomass trade from land and sea on biodiversity and ecosystem services and an improved way of identifying leverage points.
- **BIONEXT** project develops knowledge, tools, and guidance for mainstreaming biodiversity into policymaking and provides concrete options on how to initiate, accelerate and upscale biodiversity relevant transformative change in society.
- **SUSTAIN** project brings together a multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary team to strengthen understanding and awareness of how all economic activities depend and impact on biodiversity.
- **BIOTRAILS** project generates knowledge and develops tools that inspire and accelerate biodiversity-relevant transformative change in the society, taking into account four value chains of traded products.
- **RAINFOREST** project contributes to enabling, upscaling and accelerating transformative change to reduce biodiversity impacts of major food and biomass value chains. Together with stakeholders, it co-develops and evaluates just and viable transformative change pathways and interventions.
- **TC4BE** project supports transdisciplinary research on different dimensions and scales of telecoupled agrofood systems, engaging diverse stakeholders, including EU and producer-country policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities.
- **TRANSPATH** project identifies leverage points and interventions for triggering transformative changes at consumer, producer, and organizational levels. It seeks whole-of-society opportunities for achieving climate-neutrality whilst simultaneously allowing local communities and nature to flourish.

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- **BIOTraCes** project develops knowledge, tools and novel approaches that enable transformative changes (TC), necessary for achieving a nature positive society. It aims to contribute to more inclusive, effective, and just public policies, local strategies and corporate concerns on biodiversity aligned with the European Green Deal and SDGs.
- **PLANET4B** project provides insight into the diverse perceptions of biodiversity and its communication to understand behaviors and motivations around biodiversity prioritization. Existing multidisciplinary behavior theories that could be applied for biodiversity decision-making will be explored.

Cooperative relationships will be established at the first stages of the projects and maintained during their whole life through different activities, such as invitations to project meetings, connections between coordinators and partners, teleconferences to provide information and updates. This will facilitate knowledge sharing and the creation of joint products resulting from the collaboration, such as: joint attendance and/or organisation of conferences or workshops, joint scientific publications and policy briefs, and thematic guidelines. A particular focus will be given to produce common dissemination and exploitation material with shared and joint messages to support transformative action for biodiversity.

The products of such co-operation will be made visible on the website where key information and a direct URL link to sister project’s website will be published. Additionally, the BioValue newsletter will include a dedicated section where fellow projects’ news and major results/ publications can be presented.

Furthermore, BioValue will draw on existing platforms and information sharing mechanisms relevant for transformational change on biodiversity knowledge, such as Biodiversa+, the biodiversity Science Service BioAgora linked to the EC Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, the CSA, Oppla, NetworkNature) and on international expert panels on spatial planning, such as AESOP35, ACSP36 or INTA37. BioValue will also cooperate with the EU Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD) to create synergies, ensure efficient and well-targeted dialogue and dissemination, and leverage the potential impact on European policies. A preliminary list of sister projects and partnerships is provided in the table below.

Table 11 Cluster projects, fellow projects and partnerships

Cluster projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BAMBOO • CLEVER • BIONEXT • SUSTAIN • BIOTRAILS • RAINFOREST • TC4BE • TRANSPATH • BIOTraCes • PLANET4B
Fellow projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RENATURE

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EKLIPSE • ESERALDA • ROBUST • COMPASS • DREAMS • Monitoring in EIA – Nature protection and infrastructure projects in Denmark • MOBIA
<p>Partnership</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International platforms, networks and platforms (Biodiversa+, BioAgora, the CSA, Oppla, NetworkNature); • International expert panels on spatial planning (AESOP₃₅, ACSP₃₆ or INTA₃₇); • The EU Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (KCBD)

Reaching out to the stakeholders by attending events in person can effectively multiply opportunities of interaction between the project consortium and their professional target audience, enforcing the involvement in the network.

Partners will keep track of the upcoming clustering events and they will inform the rest of the members about their wish to participate on behalf of BioValue. Events attendance will be monitored through a regular communication flow happening within the consortium. Updates will be collected by ICONS on a six-month basis through a dedicated template. Examples of events include workshops, webinars, meetings. The project’s communication products will be distributed at these events to aid the partners in promoting the project. The partners’ attendance to such events will be featured in the project website and in the social media channels to ensure they get the appropriate visibility.

To enhance BioValue’s visibility, interactive webinars or/and online workshops can be organized in collaboration with the cluster projects and sector experts. Such events will become an opportunity for sharing valuable information on transformative change, spatial planning and biodiversity. Webinars will also showcase the evidence collected from the case studies, presenting the results and benefits linked to the implementation of BioValue analytical framework to possible end-users. Their recordings will be published also on Icons’ YouTube channel.

<p>Accountability</p>	<p>ICONS will be responsible for keeping track of all the events in which representatives of the BioValue partnership will participate. Also, ICONS together with the contribution of technical partners, will organize in-house events – workshops, roundtables, webinars – to showcase BioValue’s outcomes and raise awareness among a professional audience.</p>
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2.7 Management of communication and dissemination and exploitation

Responsibility in the consortium

To ensure that EU-wide communication activities can reach out to the mentioned stakeholders and the general public in order to maximise the impact and the exploitation of BioValue results, full cooperation needs to be established between the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Leader (ICONS) and the rest of the consortium. Indeed, Communication and Dissemination activities carried out locally or individually by each partner are strictly related and contribute to the project's success, especially when these activities are with relevant stakeholders and target audiences. Likewise, exploitation activities heavily relies on input from the BioValue consortium to define the project KERs and the most suitable exploitation strategy. Consequently, all the project partners are expected to fully co-operate by participating in webinars and workshops as well as answering to questionnaires and direct interviews to provide ICONS with the information necessary to define the project KERs and the most suitable exploitation strategy. More details related to partners' input to the exploitation activities and the related methodology are provided in paragraph 2.1.

The role and responsibility of ICONS, the project coordinator and all the other member of the BioValue consortium can be summarised according to the following scheme:

Table 12 BioValue's partnership accountability in communication and dissemination

Partner	Responsibility and involvement
IST-ID (coordinator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validating the proposed dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy; Providing feedback and approval on the communication and dissemination contents to be released on behalf of BioValue (i.e., project website, brochure, infopacks); Maximising the visibility of the innovation developed in the project; Ensuring that the project results have a clear societal orientation and fulfil the different stakeholders' needs.
ICONS (WP ₅ leader)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leading and coordinating dissemination, communication and exploitation activities; Developing an integrated communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy to be implemented through the project's duration; Articulating key messages to convey BioValue objectives and goals, that are based on the needs and interests of different target audiences; Developing the BioValue visual identity and communication materials e.g. flyers, info-packs, and videos; Designing, updating and maintaining the project website;

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producing the content to be published on the project website, newsletters and social media platforms as well as on external channels, with the active contribution of all the partners; • Identifying BioValue KERs; • Mapping and describing BioValue stakeholder groups and their needs; • Analysing exploitation options for the KERs; • Designing a plan with partners' joint and individual strategies for accelerating the upscaling and future uptake of BioValue analytical framework; • Delivering training on exploitation themes and activities; • Monitoring the impact of communication materials produced and distributed for BioValue.
<p>All the other BioValue partner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing contents to create the BioValue website and other communication materials; • Keeping ICONS informed as to relevant progress made by the project in their respective work packages; • Boosting BioValue' presence on social media; • Actively participating in the exploitation activities facilitated by ICONS (e.g., questionnaires, interviews, webinars, workshops); • Supporting exploitation activities providing inputs on KERs identification and description; providing IP background and foreground information and discussing the most suitable IPR management and exploitation strategy; • Contributing to stakeholder mapping activities to target dissemination and engagement activities; • Providing ICONS with the list of events and publications they will be attending on behalf of BioValue; • Mobilizing networks and connections for a wider outreach and promotion of BioValue;

Stakeholders database

The stakeholder mapping (as presented in paragraph 2.2) is the starting point for the creation of the stakeholder database.

The stakeholder database is precious for the success of dissemination activities, as it links stakeholders to key exploitable results and exploitation and dissemination strategies. It becomes particularly relevant when results worth disseminating will be ready to be disseminated. The database can be updated at any moment throughout the project.

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It does not only include GDPR-compliant information but also:

- The stakeholder type (according to the priorities identified from the stakeholder mapping);
- Stakeholder geographical level of operation;
- Relevant KERs for each stakeholder type;
- Dissemination channels and formats to use;
- Partner responsible for dissemination.

When the database is populated, partners are asked to identify stakeholder organisations they are in contact with which correspond to BioValue's key exploitable results. The same partner nominating such organisations will then be responsible for engaging directly with them and liaising with for disseminating project results at the later stages. Following this accountability scheme, more targeted messages and dissemination materials will be delivered to the specific stakeholder. Furthermore, partners – especially tasks leaders – are in charge to identify specific features or results that could be conveyed to appropriate stakeholders. As the work package leader, ICONS supervise the overall project's communication and dissemination activities and supports the individual partners in their efforts to reach out.

2.8 Monitoring

ICONS' monitoring process

The impact of BioValue's communication and dissemination products will be measured throughout the entire duration of the project. This will be done by monitoring and studying the project's ability to reach and engage with its target audiences.

Online media outreach will be calculated using a methodology that relies on automated tools that collect reliable statistics and data. The effectiveness of workshops and webinars will be measured based on the number of attendees and feedback to be collected at the end of each event.

The analytic tool called MATOMO will be used to assess the performance of the project website. It will be used extensively to retrieve available data about the traffic (in terms of the number of views, sessions, and users' behaviour) and the audience it reaches out to.

Press, news releases and journalistic articles will be monitored as well by calculating the outreach generated by the spontaneous take-ups of the BioValue' content on websites and social media channels. This reporting activity will be done using Nuvi®, social media analytics programs i.e., Twitter Analytics, Facebook Insights and YouTube Analytics and data coming from external platforms and multipliers.

ICONS' engagement indexes: CEI encompassing – PEI, SEI, WEI

Outreach and engagement indicators are not sufficient to assess the evolution of the acceptance level. On the one hand, outreach indicators provide an estimate of the audience size but not the real interest level; on the other hand, engagement indicator describe the interest and overall impacts on a community but can't be read disjointly from the outreach indicators to draw relevant

conclusions on the effective engagement. Consequently, composite indicators are considered for each area of activity: **Website Engagement Index (WEI)**, **Social media Engagement Index (SEI)** and the **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)**. They are computed as the ratio between the corresponding engagement and outreach indicators. This approach allows ICONS to analyse the communication and dissemination impacts for each area of activity separately.

The **Community Engagement Index CEI**⁹ developed by ICONS is used to integrate all communication activities into one single metric. The total engagement (outreach) value is calculated by adding together the engagement (outreach) values computed for the individual indicators.

The same ratio between the engagement and outreach values collected for each single editorial product lay behind another analysis tool developed by ICONS, namely the Impact Quadrants, as shown in the figure below. In the plot, the X and Y axes report the publication outreach and engagement values respectively. Each editorial product is represented with a bubble whose radius is given by the ratio between the corresponding engagement and outreach values. The two axes cross at the average values across the editorial products in question. The bubble distribution shows which news items have performed better in terms of outreach and engagement. This is a valuable tool for correcting and fine-tuning the BioValue's communication and dissemination strategy. The plot is dynamic, as the coordinates of the bubble vary with time as more data is collected.

The CEI will measure the actual engagement of the BioValue community via the project contents delivered on the internet and social media. It portrays the univocal relation between any project content available on the web and social media and the actual interactions of online visitors coming across that content. The CEI is a function of the outreach and engagement values, with low values of the CEI indicating little relative interest by the target audience.

⁹ Folco Giuliana, Gaboardi Elena, Lischetti Serena, Martinoli Mario, Mazzolo Giulio, & Schmid Elisabeth. (2022). Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>

Figure 6 Impact quadrant. Each bubble corresponds to an editorial publication

Accountability	ICONS will be in charge of monitoring the outreach and engagement generated by the project communication. The outcome of such exercise will be shared with the BioValue consortium at project meeting and it will feed into periodic reporting.
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2.9 Timeline

The timeline below covers the main activities for WP5 from the beginning of the project to M14 when the stakeholder mapping will be updated. The first months focus on setting up of the visual identity, social media accounts, website, and other outreach materials. In the same period, a preliminary identification of BioValue KERs and the main stakeholder groups is carried out on the basis of the project proposal and further inputs arriving from all the partners.

In addition to the activities shown in the table below, the project newsletter will be produced twice a year, usually every six months and at the most appropriate dates in terms of newsworthiness. Social media is ongoing, and the BioValue consortium has started building a community. Specific communication campaigns will also be conducted for such events as the Bioeconomy Day, The EU Green Week, the Global bioeconomy Summit. Press releases will be issued generally at milestones or for events and specific achievements or deliverables.

Table 13 Timeline

When	What	Lead beneficiary
M4	Set up of social media accounts	ICONS
M4	Website first release	ICONS
M4	Visual identity design, Brand book, ppt and deliverable templates	ICONS
M4	First press release available on BioValue’s channels	ICONS

M4	Exploitation webinar and questionnaire	ICONS
M6	Website second release	ICONS
M6	Plan for dissemination and exploitation of results (D5.1)	ICONS
M6	First newsletter set-up	ICONS
M8	Communication Kit (D5.2)	ICONS
M14	Stakeholders mapping report (D5.4)	ICONS

2.10 Visual identity

A recognizable and consistent visual identity, that includes also, but not only, the project logo, is key to reaching out effectively to stakeholders, helping the project increase its engaging capacity and impact. The BioValue's visual identity was developed starting from a brand personality exercise, which highlighted the main characteristics attributed to the project, that were: exciting, friendly, daring, unexpected and essential.

These main, heterogeneous traits represented the starting point to define how the project's partner wanted the project to be perceived by the audience and the core values they wanted to convey. The result is a visual identity that is deeply connected to three core elements driving the projects, which are:

- Transformative change, expressed by the yellow colour, as it stands for curiosity, inspiration, and confidence.
- Spatial planning, reflected by the blue colour as it conveys the idea of organization, purpose, balance and clarity.
- People, represented by the pink colour that usually symbolizes creativity, imagination, and emotions

Visually, BioValue's identity it is essential, even quite institutional, yet it includes some bold surprising elements. The three stretched circles representing the three elements also recall the idea of the underlying movement, interaction, and adaptability to reach a joint equilibrium.

Figure 7 BioValue logo

The official Brand book has been developed and shared among partners. It serves as a rulebook for everyone involved in the project, particularly when developing communication and dissemination materials for specific events including webinars. Some of the rules are shown in Annex II.

All dissemination items and publications to be released by BioValue, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union research and innovation programme and display the European emblem. All publications will include the following statement (from GA 17.3): “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

<p>Accountability</p>	<p>The BioValue logo and visual identity have been developed by ICONS with feedback from the coordinator, IST-ID (Task 5.2). All the BioValue project partners are encouraged to use the logo and the rest of the brand materials under the supervision of ICONS, following the graphic guidelines provided in the Brand book.</p>
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3 Exploitation strategy

BioValue consortium applies an impact-driven approach to ensure the sustainability and usability of the project's results. In particular, the consortium has envisioned a preliminary exploitation pathway to stimulate broader replication of KERs and engage new end-users and wider audiences, thus ensuring continuous dissemination after the project's end.

BioValue consortium includes partners from different contexts and dimensions that acts as arenas for transformation as well as research institutions and universities. The overall exploitation strategy will be based on joint synergies and activities carried out by all project's partners to maximise the exploitation of projects' results focusing on their dissemination among the scientific community, policymakers, industries and other potential end-users, and the wider public.

Key exploitable results are models, guidelines, tools as well as knowledge and expertise on how to trigger transformative change in spatial planning practices and policymaking to value biodiversity. The exploitation strategy will focus on non-commercial exploitation of the newly generated knowledge and expertise, leveraging the new internal know-how and launching new research and innovation activities, without excluding the possibility to undertake exploitation pathways, developing, for example, ancillary consultancy services for industries and other potential end-users.

The process, which has already started with the Exploitation Webinar and Questionnaire and the consequently KERs definition, will ensure that partners can, on the one hand, capitalise on the new knowledge generated during the research activities of the project and launch the new single tools and methodologies, and on the other hand develop roadmaps to upscale and replicate BioValue analytical framework. Indeed, BioValue's arenas for transformation can implement and validate the innovative solutions within their local spatial planning practices and promote biodiversity. Moreover, after the project's end, continuing R&D and further demonstrations for the optimisation and upscaling of the proposed solutions will allow for replication in different contexts and dimensions.

This roadmap will be better articulated during the project and will be completed by the end, thanks to further workshops and direct interviews with the consortium partners. At the end of the project, the roadmap will detail the key activities, resources, partnerships, and channels needed to ensure the successful uptake of results and their effective dissemination across different audiences. This will be carefully described in the D5.5 Final Exploitation plan (M36) that will be released by ICONS.

Preliminary identification of the exploitation main pathways is reported in the following paragraphs. BioValue's exploitation will be leveraged by dissemination activities and will be built upon 2 main general Exploitation pillars linked to the different partner profiles within the consortium:

- Upscaling and replication of the Biovalue framework– by public administrations, industries and other end-users;
- Academic, scientific and research exploitation – by Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs) and Universities.

Upscaling and replication of the Biovalue framework

To prepare the ground for maximized Exploitation, BioValue will leverage knowledge and experience about tools and recommendations developed within previous European funded projects and shared platforms. During the project, the integrated framework will be implemented within three different arenas for transformation. Drawing from practical experience and feedback, the actors from the three areas (Mafra Municipality, Trento Municipality and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern Federal State) will upscale the BioValue framework for enacting transformative change through spatial planning policymaking and processes and will mainstream biodiversity discourse. As part of the design of the business models to upscale the usage of the instruments included in the BioValue framework by companies in the arenas for transformation, a Business Model Canvas approach will be adopted, which also covers potential revenue gains. This will show how financial gains resulting from valuing biodiversity can sustain the implementation of transformative change within spatial planning policies.

Besides the three arenas for transformation, BioValue will disseminate the experience and knowledge gained through practice to promote the replication of the proposed solutions in additional areas and contexts and consolidate their use beyond the project's end in other domains, such as climate change. Comprehensive replication studies will focus on technical and non-technical aspects, such as Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (SP&MI), Environmental Assessment Instruments (EAI) and Economic and financing economic and financial instruments (E&FIs) (KER₂), as well as policy guidelines and recommendations for replication potentials (KER₃).

Firstly, BioValue's partners hosting the arenas for transformation will implement a strategy to upscale the demonstrated solutions within their spatial planning practices and to apply the new tools to other areas within the same Municipality or the Federal State. The direct involvement of stakeholders will allow for addressing specific needs of end-users and overcoming eventual barriers to the adoption of the new BioValue framework. This will enable to further leverage and exploit the developed solutions beyond the project's end.

Secondly, other municipalities, federal states and territories can follow the arenas for transformation best practices and replicate BioValue framework. The replication strategy will allow gaining further knowledge on the transformative potential of spatial planning tools in different sectors and in different geographical, socio-economic or regulatory contexts. Interested regions in replication will be identified thanks to dissemination activities among the members of the associations that are responsible for representing the interests of local and regional governments and mainstreaming capillary biodiversity value, reaching local authorities and citizens. Some examples are ICLEI (Local Governments for Sustainability), EUROCITIES and UCLG (United Cities and Local Governments). Moreover, the exploitation of BioValue results will be sustained by dissemination activities towards public bodies at different levels. For example, BioValue consortium will present and discuss its analytical framework and innovative solution at EU level (at EU premises and EU Parliament) to raise awareness on options for better implementation of transformative change tools within spatial planning policymaking and practice, leveraging synergies and collaborations with other funded projects from the transformative change cluster and KCBD.

Finally, in working on the upscaling of the BioValue framework within the arenas for transformation, BioValue will investigate value propositions and assess impacts on business models taking an ecosystem approach¹⁰. The outcomes of this analysis will generate key messages that will be leveraged to fine-tune the dissemination strategy towards public administrations, industries, SMEs and other potential end-users interested in adopting the BioValue tools and approach, influencing business models and value chains. To raise companies' awareness of their impacts on biodiversity and associated risks and opportunities for improvement, dedicated channels and tools for communication and dissemination will be leveraged as well as participation in relevant fora and dialogue occasions. In this phase, the role of BioValue's platform (KER2) will be pivotal for knowledge sharing.

Academic, scientific and research exploitation

BioValue overall approach and methodology consist of several research activities aiming at the selection, development and/or improvement of innovative tools enabling transformative change and biodiversity promotion, but also recommendations for optimal, integrated spatial planning process management. Therefore, BioValue entails both theoretical and applied research to develop, validate and replicate the proposed solutions.

All the partners contribute to the progress of the state-of-the-art in these fields, working cooperatively and sharing the results with the research community. BioValue aims for early and open sharing of research, especially considering the close collaboration with stakeholders through the BioValue community of interest, which will ensure that the proposed solutions meet their specific needs and bridge the gap between the scientific community and decision-makers.

Such activities will be carried out by the following partners, in close cooperation with actors from the arenas for transformation: University of Lisbon - Instituto Superior Técnico - IST-ID, Aalborg University – AAU, Trento University – UniTrento, and Helmholtz Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ. They will exploit the acquired knowledge about:

- Environmental and sustainability science, integrating fields such as landscape ecology, planning theory, spatial analysis;
- Economic and financial Assessment, Social Impact Assessment and Environmental Impact Assessment;
- Multicriteria analysis and spatial decision support systems;
- Governance, policy, and transformative change towards sustainability.

They will leverage the knowledge developed within the BioValue project for scientific publications and for further scientific and research developments. Indeed, research centres and universities in the project plan to leverage KERs in new projects, integrate them into urban and spatial planning courses and create opportunities for new researcher within the involved organisations.

¹⁰ Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2004) The Ecosystem Approach, (CBD Guidelines) Montreal: Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity 50 p.

Moreover, the body of knowledge and expertise developed within BioValue can be applied in different contexts across Europe other than the ones represented by BioValue's arenas for transformation, fuelling knowledge transfer, research collaboration and further research projects, besides academic exploitation. Indeed, the developed solutions can be adapted, applied and upscaled not only within the arenas for transformation, but also to other contexts and in relation to other topics, such as climate change.

The nature of BioValue's KERs will mainly entail non-commercial exploitation pathways, however BioValue's partners can also consider commercial strategy options to maximise project's impacts. Indeed, universities and research institutes as well as socio-economic experts and environment practitioners and professionals can capitalize on the knowledge generated within the BioValue project and launch new system models for transformative change, innovative solutions and consultancy services, whose business opportunities can be evaluated during the project's execution. For example, new tools and models (KER₁, KER₂) can be embedded in partners' commercial consulting projects and services to public administrations, industries, SMEs and other potential end-users willing to implement transformative change tools for valuing biodiversity.

In any case, the BioValue consortium will exert efforts, whenever possible, to make data and other research results available through open services. Scientific publications from the project will be published in Open Access Journals. Other research outputs like raw data, tools and methodologies will be considered for protection by soft IP measures, in accordance with confidentiality agreements and Intellectual Property Rights and in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation. The definition of the exploitation strategies and IP measures will be designed starting from the general principles envisioned by BioValue consortium in the Grant Agreement and consolidated in the Final Exploitation Plan (D5.5, M36).

4 Conclusions

This Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results presents the overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy of BioValue.

Partners can refer to this deliverable to align their local communication to project one, as it provides visual and content guidelines. Also, it provides an overview of the main tools and channels to be used for dissemination of project results, as well as the monitoring strategy that will be developed. The channels and formats illustrated in the current deliverable will ensure awareness, engagement and uptake between professional stakeholders and the general public. Their efficiency and outreach will be monitored periodically thereby allowing the project to understand and fine-tune its contents and the overall Communication and Dissemination strategy over time.

This document also contains the premise of the exploitation strategy, starting from the preliminary identification of KERs and stakeholder groups. Partners can find in this document the methodology that will be applied to define joint and individual exploitation strategies and the steps that will be carried out to ensure an effective and sustainable exploitation of project results.

The current deliverable will be updated throughout the whole project to fine-tune the strategy. The exploitation strategy will be consolidated at the end of the project, providing a comprehensive view of exploitation strategies and target segments in the Final Exploitation Plan (D5.5, M36), while a detailed Stakeholder Mapping Report (D5.4) will be released at M14.

Annex I – Exploitation Questionnaire

This annex shows the BioValue Exploitation Questionnaire that was distributed after the Exploitation Webinar. It was developed by ICONS to collect some preliminary information on Key Exploitable Results and Exploitation Strategy from BioValue's partners.

	QUESTIONS	INSTRUCTIONS
	Partner Name	Name of the partner filling in the questionnaire
EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	Result Name	Name of the result
	Individual - Joint Result	Choose between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> INDIVIDUAL RESULTS: carried out/developed by single partners; JOINT RESULTS: developed jointly by more than one partner, that should agree upon the accessibility, usage & exploitation.
	Result Description	Description of the result
	Partner's role and contribution	In case of a joint result, please, explain your role and the contribution you will bring to the result, in terms of IP background (data, information, knowledge).
IP & IPR	Type of access	What type of access to the result do you envisage? Choose between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OPEN: if the result will be fully open to the public and used for scientific and knowledge transfer; CLOSED: if the result will be kept private and confidential and used for further internal research and development.
	IP Ownership Background	Which are partners owning IP of background information? Partner x, y, z. The background IP owners are the partners that provide initial inputs (data, information, knowledge) for the generation of the result. A partner can provide initial inputs but not being the final owner of the result.
	IP Ownership Foreground	Which are partners owning IP of foreground information? Partner x, y, z. The foreground IP owners are the final owners of the result. If more partners contributed to it, they must be listed here.
	Expected measures to protect IP	Which measures do you expect to protect IP (if any)? Choose from the list.

		As discussed during the webinar, we mainly expect potential patents and copyright in scientific publications. In some cases, though, the way a result will be leveraged inside an organisation could be protected as know-how and/or confidential information (so called SOFT IP)
REPLICABILITY	Replicability/Upscaling potential	Do you have replicability/upscaling plans? Please explain if the project result can be replicated in other contexts and describe how third parties can leverage the results for their own scopes.
EXPLOITATION HINTS	Planned use: partner's exploitation strategy	How do you plan to exploit the result after project's end? Please provide some insights. E.g., use the result for further research, to participate in other EU funded projects, to integrate it in university courses, to enhance your research services, licensing, dissemination through scientific publications, events, conferences...)
	Target segment(s)	Which are results' target segments? And early adopters? E.g., general public, research institutions, policy makers, public institutions, universities...
	Target segment's use	How early adopters/identified target segments can use and leverage the result? E.g., leveraging the information in their decision-making process, applying recommendations; using the produced knowledge in further research activities...

Annex II – Brand book

This annex shows the BioValue Brand book. It was developed by ICONS to summarise the main aspects of the project's visual identity.

Visual Identity Values

Visual Identity value

Visual identity consists of values, strategies and visual elements (logo, colours, images).

It is not a matter of aesthetics: the main purpose is to make BioValue project recognizable and unique at first glimpse.

Visual identity is not just about the logo: it assures consistency and clear identification in every communication to deliver, raising trust and reputation of the project in front of stakeholders, media and people.

The BioValue visual identity is the result of a joint process starting with a brand identity exercise to grasp the main elements of the BioValue essence. **Even about its identity, BioValue strives for equilibrium, and it reaches it balancing very different traits.**

Indeed, from the exercise, the unexpected, exciting, and daring nature of the project emerged, along with its essentiality and formalism.

These main, heterogeneous traits represented our starting point to work on how we wanted the project to be perceived by the audience and the core values we wanted to convey. The result is a visual identity that is deeply connected to the core element driving the projects, which are transformative change, spatial planning, and people. Visually, it is essential, even quite institutional, yet it includes some bold surprising elements.

Main landmark

Main landmark

The circle was the form we started working with: it gives the idea of fullness, accomplishment, and equilibrium.
BioValue is a project about transformative change that considers interactions among many players and factors in spatial planning. Therefore, we wanted to make key concepts like change, dynamism, and interaction visible. We used a circle: we multiplied it, stretched it, and deformed it. Finally, we reach a new equilibrium that is given by the interaction of three different shapes, representing people, change and spatial planning. These are the three core values of BioValue and each of them, to be in equilibrium needs to make room for and adapt to the others.

Three is a recursive number within the BioValue projects. Three are the complementary instrumental perspectives that will be explored to mainstream biodiversity concerns across all sectors affected by spatial planning; and also the arenas for transformations that explore in practice the transformative potential of spatial planning processes for increasing biodiversity values to society. The three shapes are an easy reminder of these multiple aspects.

BioValue

Logo variants

Monochromatic
Brandmark

Brandmark on colour
background

When the background is coloured, please use white version of the brandmark.

Brand identity colours

Colors

Colours make and convey sense to the BioValue visual identity. Of course, multiple colours are essentials to convey the wide range of interests, value systems and political levels impacted by the project. As we did with the shapes, we opted for using three different colours to convey the BioValue core values:

- Pink represents people, as it usually symbolizes creativity, imagination, and emotions.
- Blue represents spatial planning, as it conveys the idea of organization, purpose, balance and clarity
- Yellow represents change, as it stands for curiosity, inspiration, and confidence.

Besides the logo, another colour that is recursive and particularly meaningful in the BioValue visual identity is purple. Purple means wisdom, and imagination but also harmony and it works well as an overarching colour.

These same colours enter also the images collected from the arenas for transformation. Images of natural places and landscapes are presented with unexpected pops of colours, conveying the sense of transformative change concept itself and the impact that the BioValue results will have on space planning and biodiversity.

People Pink: #ff46a5 C 0
R 255 M 80 Y 0
G 70 K 0
B 165

Space Blu: #2378ff C 80
R 30 M 55 Y 0
G 120 K 0
B 255

Inspiration Yellow: #ffaa0f C 0
R 255 M 40 Y 90
G 170 K 0
B 15

Unexpected Purple: #5a37b9 C 80
R 90 M 80 Y 0
G 85 K 0
B 185

Pictures treatment

Typography

Typeface

Titles: Argent Light

0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Body: Aaux Next Regular

0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Aaux Next Regular Italic

0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Aaux Next Bold

0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

On MS-Office "Times New Roman" should be used for titles and "Verdana" for body text as alternate fonts.

